

Use of EDTA for Potentiometric Back-titration of Rare Earths and Analysis of their Mixtures

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Advantage was taken of the stoichiometric reaction between mercury(II), rare earths, alkaline earths, heavy metal ions and EDTA in urotropine buffered media to determine rare earths by back-titration of excess EDTA in the course of estimating a variety of lanthanides or analysing their binary mixture with one of the alkaline earth metals by selective control of pH; or analysing their binary mixtures with heavy metals using fluoride as a good masking agent for rare earths; or analysing their ternary mixtures with both heavy and alkaline earth metals in two steps, one by selective control of pH and the other by masking of rare earths with fluoride at lower pH to estimate the heavy metal. The procedures given are simple, rapid and extremely reliable.

KHALIFA and coworkers^{1,2} determined with fair accuracy La, Pr, and Y by potentiometric back-titration of excess EDTA in solutions buffered with ammonium nitrate-ammonium hydroxide at pH 8-10, with standard mercury(II) nitrate solution using silver amalgam as the indicator electrode. The obtained potential breaks were in average 90 mV per 0.1 ml of 0.05 M titrant. The aim of the present work is to apply the method suggested by Khalifa to the potentiometric determination of rare earths alone or in binary mixtures using hexamine buffers instead of ammoniacal ones. Hexamine has the advantage over ammonia as it gives higher potential breaks amounting to 210 mV per 0.1 ml of 0.05 M titrant³. In ammoniacal buffer the half-cell reaction,

indicates that the concentration of free Hg^{2+} ions added just beyond the end-point of titrating excess EDTA with Hg^{2+} (0.05 ml of 0.05 M Hg) will be reduced to an appreciable extent by combination with NH_3 molecules. Thus the potential breaks, which according to Nernst equation depends essentially on free Hg^{2+} ions concentration, will be much smaller in magnitude in comparison with those obtained in hexamine buffers. The rare earths have been determined by EDTA titration methods using a variety of indicators including eriochrome black T at pH⁴ 8-9, alizarin red S screened with methylene blue at pH^{5,6} 4, xylenol orange at pH⁷⁻⁹ 5, arsenazo at pH¹⁰ 5.5, bromopyrogallol red¹¹, arsenazo(III)¹², catechol green¹³, PAN¹⁴, SPAN¹⁵ and methylthymol blue¹⁶. The most recent report about analysis of rare earth mixtures is given by Zayed *et al.*¹⁷.

Experimental

All chemicals used in this investigation were of the highest purity available, which included oxides of samarium, praseodymium, gadolinium, ytterbium, europium, dysprosium, holmium, terbium, erbium, lanthanum and zinc; hydroxide, fluoride and acetate of sodium; hydroxide and chloride of ammonium; nitric and acetic acids; disodium salt of ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid (EDTA), mercuric nitrate, hexamethylenetetramine (hexamine), calcium carbonate, pyridine, eriochrome black T (EBT), murexide, methylthymol blue, arsenazo and xylenol orange indicators.

Double-distilled from all-glass equipment were used.

Solutions: The 0.0103-0.0526 M mercuric nitrate solutions were prepared from a nitrate sample and standardised against EDTA using methylthymol blue as indicator. The hexamine buffer solutions were prepared by dissolving hexamine (100 g) in double-distilled water (1 dm³) and adjusting with 0.5 M NaOH or 0.25 M nitric acid to the desired pH. The 0.00139-0.00085 M Gd, 0.00188-0.0087 M Pr, 0.002-0.0089 M Sm, 0.00176 and 0.00818 M La, 0.002 and 0.0091 M Er, 0.002 and 0.009 M Tb, 0.0021 and 0.0094 M Ho, 0.0017 and 0.0073 M Eu, 0.002 and 0.0091 M Yt, and 0.0021 and 0.0097 M Dy nitrate solutions were prepared from the oxide samples by dissolving in least amount of 1:1 hot nitric acid and diluting with water to the appropriate volumes. The resulting solutions were standardised against EDTA solution using arsenazo or xylenol orange indicators.

Titration cell: It consisted of a pyrex glass vessel fitted with a glass cover provided with ground

joints for the silver amalgam electrode, the calomel and the tip of the buret. A W.G. PYE (Cambridge Cat. no. 7902/5) Scalamp galvanometer connected to a PYE student potentiometer with a potential range 0–1 800 mV, were used. A Orion Research 701 A/digital pH/mV meter with a combination pH electrode Orion 91-02 was used for pH adjustment.

Procedures :

Procedure I : The procedure I applied to the determination of rare earths involved back-titrating excess EDTA in presence of rare earth versenate, in hexamine buffer of pH 8–11, with mercuric ion solution using silver amalgam as the indicator electrode.

Procedure II : The procedure II applied for the analysis of mixtures with zinc involved masking of rare earths with 0.05 M sodium fluoride then back-titrating excess EDTA for determination of zinc, and back titrating another identical mixture in absence of fluoride for the total, with mercuric ion solution

Procedure III : The procedure III applied for analysis of mixtures with calcium involved back-titration of excess EDTA at pH 11 for determination of the total, then lowering the pH to 7.5 with nitric acid and titration of the liberated EDTA equivalent to calcium is continued with mercuric ions solution.

Procedure IV : The procedure IV used for analysis of ternary mixtures with calcium and zinc involved back-titrating excess EDTA at pH 11 for determination of the total, then adjusting to pH 7.5 with nitric acid and titrating the liberated EDTA equivalent to calcium, with mercuric ion solution. In another identical mixture, the rare earth was masked with sodium fluoride, the pH was adjusted to 7.5 to mask calcium, and zinc was determined by back-titrating excess EDTA with mercuric ion solution.

Results and Discussion

That relatively smaller end-point potential breaks are obtained in ammoniacal buffers, was shown by Reilly *et al.*^{1,2} to be due to the fact that in the case of a complexing agent as ammonia, the potential of a mercury electrode, the silver amalgam electrode corresponds at pH values less than 9 to the reaction,

and its value is given by

$$E_{\text{Hg}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Hg}^0} = E_{\text{Hg}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Hg}^0}^0 + 0.0296 \log \frac{[\text{Hg}(\text{NH}_3)_2^{2+}][\text{H}^+]^2}{K K_a^2 [\text{NH}_3]^2}$$

where, K_a is the acidity constant of NH_4^+ ion and K the stability constant of the mercury–ammonia complex. Calculating its stability constant by aid

of the above equation gave a log K value of 17.6. Thus there will be a competition between ammonia and EDTA for the Hg^{2+} ions, and the indirect complex effect of ammonia will contribute strongly to the shifting of potential to the oxygen sensitive range.

Determination of rare earths : In the back-titration of excess EDTA with mercuric ions for determination of lanthanum at different pH values 8–11, the maximum potential breaks detecting the end-point was observed at pH 10 and found to be 220 mV/0.1 ml titrant. Similar results were obtained for the other rare earths. This observation was in harmony with the results obtained by Khalifa³. The breaks lying in the immediate vicinity of the expected end-points ranged 126–240 mV/0.1 ml of 0.0103–0.0526 M Hg^{2+} . From these results it is apparent that potential inflections are sharp enough to permit accurate determination of end-points. The mean deviation, the relative mean deviation, the standard deviation and the coefficient of variation in the determination of 5.68 mg of La were found to be 0.02, 0.35, 0.034 and 0.59%, respectively. The relative percent errors, in most cases, do not exceed 1% for determination of 0.2–21 mg of rare earths. The maximum standard deviation for these elements does not exceed ± 0.09 indicating high accuracy of the present method. The present method has the advantage over the classical volumetric methods of end-points determination which suffer from error due to reversible indicator colour reaction at the end-point. Moreover, the present method has the advantage over the previous work of Khalifa *et al.*^{1,2} for the higher potential breaks obtained at the vicinity of end-point which enable determination of the end-point with fair accuracy.

Analysis of binary mixtures containing rare earths with zinc : In these titrations the potential breaks were large enough to permit accurate determination of the end points and amounted in average to 200 and 240 mV/0.1 ml of 0.05 or 0.0526 M Hg^{2+} in absence and in presence of fluoride. This was in accordance with results obtained by Khalifa³. The analysis of such a mixture depends essentially upon the fact that the rare earths can be precipitated quantitatively as fluoride. Thus adding excess of fluoride will mask the rare earths and will enable the other cation to be determined with fair accuracy. The maximum percent errors were 1.69 and 0.00 for rare earths and zinc respectively indicating high accuracy of the present method.

Analysis of binary mixtures containing rare earths with calcium : These titrations were characterised by sharp potential breaks lying in the immediate vicinity of the expected end-points and amounting an average of 75 and 170 mV/0.1 ml of Hg^{2+} at pH 11 and 7.5 respectively. Analysis of such a mixture was based upon the instability of alkaline earth versenates at lower pH. Thus, the total cation content can be determined at higher pH and then

lowering the pH to liberate a quantity of EDTA equivalent to calcium. The maximum percent errors were found to be 1.69 and 0.00 for rare earths and calcium, respectively, indicating high accuracy of the method.

Analysis of ternary mixtures containing rare earths: The potential breaks lying in the immediate vicinity of the three end-points were of excellent order of magnitude amounting on an average to 80, 180 and 230 mV/0.1 ml of 0.05–0.0524 M Hg²⁺, which enabled determination of the end-points with fair accuracy. The maximum percent errors were 0.83, 0.61 and 0.77 for rare earths, zinc and calcium, respectively.

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